

ASPECTS OF LIMINALITY AND THE FIGURE OF THE TRICKSTER IN P.L. TRAVERS'S *MARY POPPINS* NOVELS¹

Abstract: Drawing on Arnold van Gennep's and Victor Turner's definition and description of liminality as well as William J. Hynes and William G. Doty's understanding and characterization of the archetypal trickster figure, this paper discusses aspects of liminality: periods of transition and liminal spaces, as well as the character of Mary Poppins as a liminal trickster figure in P.L. Travers's *Mary Poppins* novels.

Keywords: liminality, trickster, P.L. Travers, Mary Poppins

P.L. Travers's *Mary Poppins* series (eight volumes² altogether), center on the adventures of the middle-class Banks children and their magical nanny in Edwardian London. The author, interested in mythology, eastern religions and philosophy, focused her narrative on the children's experience of the spiritual and the supernatural, imparting lessons about the meanings of the universe, rather than promoting social skills or teaching moral values. Mary Poppins, the eponymous protagonist of the books, and the outwardly strict nanny of the Banks children, claims kinship with various animals, mythological figures and supernatural creatures and is, in fact, a trickster: a boundary crosser, who challenges her protégés to use their intuition and imagination to liberate themselves from within. Drawing on Arnold van Gennep's and Victor Turner's definition and description of liminality as well as on William J. Hynes and William G. Doty's understanding and characterization of the archetypal trickster figure, this paper discusses aspects of liminality (both spatial and temporal) as they appear in the *Mary Poppins* books as well as the figure of Mary Poppins as a trickster.

1. Liminality and the Figure of the Trickster

¹ The fragments that are cited from Travers's *Mary Poppins* novels are taken from the Kindle edition of P.L. Travers's *Mary Poppins: The Complete Collection*. As page numbers are not available, the parenthetical citations specify only the title of the novel and the number and title of the chapter from which a specific quote is taken.

² *Mary Poppins* (1934), *Mary Poppins Comes Back* (1935), *Mary Poppins Opens the Door* (1943), *Mary Poppins in the Park* (1952), *Mary Poppins from A to Z* (1963), *Mary Poppins in the Kitchen* (1975), *Mary Poppins in Cherry Tree Lane* (1982), *Mary Poppins and the House Next Door* (1988)

The words liminal and liminality are derived from the Latin “limen,” which means “threshold”. The idea was introduced to the field of anthropology in 1909 by Arnold Van Gennep in his seminal work: *The Rites of Passage*. Van Gennep described rites of passage, such as coming-of-age rituals and marriage, as having the following three-part structure: separation, liminal period, and re-assimilation. The initiate (the person undergoing the ritual) is first stripped of the social status that he or she possessed before the ritual, inducted into the liminal period of transition, and finally given his or her new status and re-assimilated into society.

It was not until the second half of the 20th century, though, that the terms “liminal” and “liminality” gained popularity through the writings of Victor Turner. Turner first introduced his interpretation of liminality in 1967, drawing heavily on Van Gennep’s three-part structure for ‘rites of passage’. He focused entirely on the middle stage of rites of passage—the transitional or liminal stage. He noted that “the subject of passage ritual” was “in the liminal period, structurally, if not physically, ‘invisible’” (Turner, 95). That is, the status of liminal individuals was socially and structurally ambiguous. He developed this idea further in a concise definition of liminality: “Liminality may perhaps be regarded as the Nay to all positive structural assertions, but as in some sense the source of them all, and, more than that, as a realm of pure possibility whence novel configurations of ideas and relations may arise” (Turner, 97).

Turner also pointed out that liminal individuals were polluting, and thus dangerous, to those who had not gone through the liminal period. In addition, liminal individuals had “no status, insignia, secular clothing, rank, and kinship position, nothing to demarcate them structurally from their fellows” (Turner, 98). While in the liminal state, human beings were stripped of anything that might have differentiated them from their fellow human beings — they were in between the social structures, and that it was in the gaps and intervals between two well-defined social structures that they became most aware of themselves. Turner perceived liminality as a “midpoint of transition... between two positions” and as a temporary phase rather than a permanent state.

In the present paper liminality is used in both in its spatial and its temporal sense; that is, as a tangible transitional terrain and as a state of transition or liminal chronotope.

There are as many definitions of tricksters as myths and stories told about them or scholars engaged in studying them, typical identifications of the trickster, as they are represented in myths and literature, including animal-person (Coyote, Crow, Fox, Hare, Rabbit, Raven, Spider, Tortoise), demi-god, picaro, buffoon, swindler etc. For some scholars such as Radin and Jung the trickster figure is a transcendental or "archetypal" characteristic of the human psyche. Hence the figure represents a sort of primitive developmental level common to humanity, He is associated typically with organizing the natural world.

The overwhelming majority of all so-called trickster myths in North America give an account of the creation of the earth, or at least the transforming of the world, and have a hero who is always wandering, who is always hungry, who is not guided by normal

conceptions of good or evil, who is either playing tricks on people or having them played on him (...). (Radin 155)

For Joseph Campbell the trickster is a “super-shaman” (275) capable of shape-shifting and civilizing, a culture hero and magical creature that is present in all the mythologies of the world. For yet other scholars, such as Ugo Bianchi, the trickster is a demiurgic creator. According to William J. Hynes the difficulty of pinning down the figure of the trickster resides in the fact that tricksters by their nature are liminal creatures, who resist any attempt at classification or setting of boundaries: “the sheer richness of trickster phenomena can easily lead one to conclude that the trickster is indefinable. In fact, to define (de-finis) is to draw borders around phenomena, and tricksters seem amazingly resistant to such capture; they are notorious border breakers” (Hynes 33).

Yet, for all the variety of forms that they may adopt, tricksters, who are mythical (and not modern) creatures, have consistent personalities. Their personalities do not change or develop over the course of a tale, and the focus of the tale is not on how outside forces influence these characters to change, as is often the case in modern literature, but on how the characters’ consistent personality allows them to deal with the world. According to W.J. Hynes there are six characteristics that all trickster share. These are the following: “ambiguous and anomalous personality” (34), “deceiver and trick player” (35), “shapeshifter” (36), “situation-inventor” (37), “messenger and imitator of the gods” (39), and “sacred and lewd bricoleur” (42).

For liminal mythic characters, like the trickster, liminality is their original state. Since liminality is betwixt and between the social structures, their existence in liminality allows them access to the social structure at any number of points. The trickster may flit across the borders at any time, penetrating the social structure at will, but he cannot stay there. He must return to that state of betwixt and between in order to manifest his powers.

It is not only the trickster’s nature as a mythic character that allows him to remain in liminality; it is also the mythic world that he inhabits that makes this possible. As mythic characters, tricksters impose their will on the world around them. In the modern era, though, the individual struggles against a much more powerful world, one that will not tolerate the imposition of will, at least not to the same extent. Thus it is interesting to see what happens to this mythic archetype when it is transplanted into a modern world.

2. Mary Poppins: the Nanny as Trickster

Chronologically the *Mary Poppins* novels are set in England in transition between the Victorian and Edwardian period. While this fact may certainly be an explanation of the Janus-faced values promoted in the narrative – the observation of rules and the cultivation of obedience and perfect manners when in view and under the control of adults, and the reclaiming of freedom and the pursuit of adventures in the periods of the day (at night, for instance) when, and in places (the park, the zoo etc.) where control weakens – it also accounts for the curious, liminal position that Mary Poppins occupies in the middle-class Banks family, as nanny for their children.

According to Katherine Holden, in the course of the 19th c. and in the first half of the 20th nannies occupied a strange, liminal position in upper and middle-class households: that between the children's mother or parents and the rest of the household staff. The nanny was half parent and half servant; half familiar and half stranger. While this separateness was desired and seen as necessary if upper- and middle-class parents wanted to keep their children away from their own everyday lives, nannies represented a form of "beyond" in the eyes of the families they served, because of their obscure origins and liminal social status within the household. Furthermore, the figure of the nanny and/or the governess was paradoxical from the point of view of the children, for the latter were supposed to be kept under strict control by a person who had no real authority over them, and whose strange position within the family exposed the very arbitrary nature of official adult norms, schemes and values. Consequently, many children refused to obey their nannies and/ or governesses.

In P.L. Travers's *Mary Poppins* novels, before the arrival of Mary Poppins, the Banks children: Jane and Michael, the twins: John and Barbara, and, later on, the baby Annabel as well, are unruly and rebellious: the scare of the nannies, who are unable to control them, but also of their parents: of their overworked father, who plans to board a ship and sail the South Seas or to hide from them in a cave, and of their mother, who, overwhelmed by her domestic and social duties, writes desperate letters to newspapers to place advertisements for a new nanny. Obviously, only a person possessing outstanding qualities, would be able to bring order into the life of this chaotic family.

From her advent to the Banks household, Mary Poppins introduces herself to the children (but not to their parents) as a border-crosser, and defier of the laws of physics: she is brought to the gate by the wind, can slide up on bannisters, and packs out huge objects, such as a camp bed, from a seemingly empty carpet bag. Her authority as a superior (supposedly magic) creature, is thus established. From the viewpoint of the parents, she is a highly competent and efficient nursemaid, a fashionable and well-mannered respectable young woman. Even the servants: Mrs. Brill, the cook, and Ellen, the maid, who are more prone to adopt a critical attitude towards the governess, acknowledge that somehow, since the day of her arrival, all things go better

While obviously the cause of a series of magical happenings and outstanding adventures, Mary Poppins is not the customary fairy. She does not cast spells, does not wave a magic wand, and does not plot to perform magic in any conventional way. It is as if magic occurred in her presence as a matter of fact. She is vain, obsessed with her dress and her looks (She constantly admires her own reflection in shop windows.) but not beautiful: "Jane and Michael could see that the newcomer had shiny black hair – "Rather like a wooden Dutch doll," whispered Jane. And that she was thin, with large feet and hands, and small, rather peering blue eyes." (Travers: *Mary Poppins*, "Chapter One: East Wind") She is conservative as regarding the children's outward behavior and deference towards herself, but at the same time revolutionizes the family by exposing her charges to supernatural adventures that liberate them from the very manners and social rules she herself told them to obey.

Mary Poppins is a modern, feminine variant of the ancient mythical figure of the trickster. Though she does not violate gastronomic, scatological or sexual taboos, which any traditional male trickster would definitely do, she does share the basic six characteristics of tricksters.

Firstly, she is an ambiguous and anomalous personality. She is the eternal visitor and/ or drifter who resists to be pinned down, defined or explained.

“And you, Mary Poppins,” Jane demanded, knowing that it was a daring question. “Where is your home – East or West? Where do you go when you’re not here?” ...
“I’m at home,” she said, “wherever I am!” (Travers: *Mary Poppins and the House Next Door*)

She is a nanny that teaches the children manners, provides them with a sense of security but at the same time allures them to leave the security of the nursery after bedtime and take an adventure in possibly dangerous places, like the park or the zoo, to offer her protégés lessons of an existential nature. She manifests both parental care:

Up and down the Nursery went Mary Poppins, tucking them all in. They could smell her old familiar smell, a mixture of toast and starchy aprons. They could feel her old familiar shape, solid and real beneath her clothes. They watched her in adoring silence, drinking her in. (Travers: *Mary Poppins Opens the Door*, “Chapter One: The Fifth of November”)

and harsh punitive behavior: she banishes Jane into the painted world of a Royal Doulton Bowl, as punishment for Jane’s rebelling against the duties that befell her as the eldest daughter.

“So!” said the shadowy figure, taking a long curved pipe from his mouth. “Jane has arrived at last.” (...)

“She came through the alder wood with the boys, Great-Grandfather,” said Christina.

“Ah? How did they catch her?”

“She was cross at being the eldest. So she threw her paint-box at the Bowl and cracked Val’s knee.”

“So!” the horrible old voice whistled. “It was temper, was it? Well, well—” He laughed thinly. “Now you’ll be the youngest, my dear! My youngest Great-Granddaughter. But I shan’t allow any tempers here! Heh! Heh! Heh! Oh, dear, no. Well, come along and sit by the fire. Will you take Tea or Cherry – Wine?”

“No, no!” Jane burst out. “I’m afraid there’s been a mistake. I must go home now. I live at Number Seventeen Cherry Tree Lane.”

“Used to, you mean,” corrected Val triumphantly. “You live here now.”

“But you don’t understand!” Jane said desperately. “I don’t want to live here. I want to go home.”

“Nonsense!” croaked the Great-Grandfather. “Number Seventeen is a horrible place, mean and stuffy and modern. Besides, you’re not happy there. Heh! Heh! Heh! I know what it’s like being the eldest – all the work and none of the fun. Heh! Heh! But here –” he waved his pipe – “here you’ll be the Spoilt One, the Darling, the Treasure, and never go back any more!”

“Never!” echoed William and Everard, dancing round her. (...)

“No, no!” cried Jane. “It’s not true! It can’t be.” Her heart was thumping inside her. Never to see Michael again, nor the Twins, nor her Father and Mother and Mary Poppins! And suddenly she began to shout, lifting her voice so that it echoed wildly through the stone corridors.

“Mary Poppins! I’m sorry I was cross! Oh, Mary Poppins, help me, help me!” (Travers: *Mary Poppins Comes Back*, “Chapter Three: Bad Wednesday”)

Secondly, Mary Poppins is a deceiver and trick player. While, she is “the prima causa of disruptions and disorders” (Hynes 35) in the lives of the Banks children, she never admits responsibility, and acts offended by any intimation of her involvement. After having lured the children from their beds at night to her own outlandish birthday celebration at the Zoo, an occasion at which animals walked freely and acted like humans, while people were on display in the cages, Mary Poppins denies any involvement and is indignant when Jane asks her about it:

“Mary Poppins,” she said, looking very hard at her, “were you at the Zoo last night?”

Mary Poppins’ eyes popped.

“At the Zoo? In the middle of the night? Me? A quiet orderly person who knows that early to bed, early to rise makes a man healthy, wealthy and wise?”

“But *were* you?” Jane persisted.

“I have all I need of zoos in this nursery, thank you,” said Mary Poppins uppishly. “Hyenas, orangutans, all of you. Sit up straight, and no more nonsense.” (Travers: *Mary Poppins*, “Chapter Ten: Full Moon”)

Thirdly, Mary Poppins is a shapeshifter. Though not in the usual way of animal-person tricksters, Mary Poppins is able to modify the dimensions of her body to fit in a variety of spaces, and, while she is never seen to change into any kind of animal, she claims kinship with talking polar bears, lions, snakes and giant turtles. Moreover, she speaks the language of all the animals (we see her conversing with starlings, cats, and the Banks’s wealthiest neighbor: Miss Larks’s dogs) and natural phenomena (such as the wind), with stars (the Sun) and various planets.

Fourthly, Mary Poppins is a situation invertor. Mary Poppins definitely can turn things upside down. While usually she tries to bring order to chaos, managing the daily routine of the children in the nursery, on the street and in the park, delivering praises and punishments whenever she feels they are needed and/or appropriate, this trickster nanny functions as a social safety valve for the children, as well. She always gives them the opportunity to let off steam by making them meet specific characters: three of her funny and magic uncles, all craftsmen, who under the pretense of mending various broken objects of the Banks household, encourage the children to act foolishly: laugh freely, stand on their heads, and dance to their own tunes. The visits at Mary Poppins’s uncles are energizing and refreshing not only in a psychological sense but physically as well, for the children feel so easy that in all three cases (there are three visits) they lift in the air:

Jane and Michael, though they were trying hard to be polite, just couldn’t help doing what they did. They laughed. *And* they laughed. They shut their mouths tight to prevent the laughter escaping, but that didn’t do any good. And presently they were rolling over and over on the floor, squealing and shrieking with laughter.

“Really!” said Mary Poppins. “Really, *such* behaviour!”

“I can’t help it, I can’t help it!” shrieked Michael, as he rolled into the fender. “It’s so terribly funny. Oh, Jane, *isn’t* it funny?”

Jane did not reply, for a curious thing was happening to her. As she laughed she felt herself growing lighter and lighter, just as though she were being pumped full of air. It was a curious and delicious feeling and it made her want to laugh all the more. And then suddenly, with a bouncing bounce, she felt herself jumping through the air. Michael, to his astonishment, saw her go soaring up through the room. With a little bump her head touched the ceiling and then she went bouncing along it till she reached Mr Wigg. (Travers: *Mary Poppins*, “Chapter Three: Laughing Gas”)

Fifthly, Mary Poppins is an imitator and messenger of the gods. Besides the fact she is related to several animals that act as if they were deities, Mary Poppins claims kinship with or/and befriends constellations, planets and stars. She commands the winds, and takes part in the creation process by helping the centuries-old mythical lady: Mrs. Corry and her two giant daughters bring more light to the night by gluing stars onto the sky. Furthermore, Mary Poppins is venerated by all the entities (animate and inanimate) of the universe: her birthdays are ritualistic celebrations, and her bimonthly day-outs from the house of the Banks family are opportunities to visit alternative universes and realms. As a rule, she takes her older charges: Jane and Michael with her on these exploits, offering the children the possibility of ritual rebellion in lieu of actual rebellion, and thus rendering their real and secluded life more interesting and bearable. The adventures take place after bedtime, and/or in spaces outside the nursery: the park, the zoo. During these outings that always occur on special days, when, according to ancient Celtic belief, the veil between the real and the spiritual world is lifted (Full Moon, Halloween, the eve of Midsummer etc.) the children are given lessons on the meanings of the universe. They are taught about the radically human character of the cosmos, and realise that their daily world is more than meets the eye, more complex and interesting: a multidimensional plane of being, a dance in which all beings: human and nonhuman, animate and inanimate meet and move together in a single pattern:

Birds and animals were now swaying together, closely encircling Mary Poppins, who was rocking lightly from side to side. Backwards and forwards went the swaying crowd, keeping time together, swinging like the pendulum of a clock. Even the trees were bending and lifting gently, and the moon seemed to be rocking in the sky as a ship rocks on the sea.

“Bird and beast and stone and star – we are all one, all one—” murmured the Hamadryad, softly folding his hood about him as he himself swayed between the children.

“Child and serpent, star and stone – all one.”

The hissing voice grew softer. The cries of the swaying animals dwindled and became fainter. Jane and Michael, as they listened, felt themselves gently rocking too, or as if they were being rocked. . . (Travers: *Mary Poppins*, “Chapter Ten: Full Moon”)

Last but not least, though not lewd or/and sacred, Mary Poppins is a bricoleur. According to W. J. Hynes,

the bricoleur is a tinker or fix-it person, noted for his ingenuity in transforming anything at hand in order to form a creative solution. Because the established definitions or usage categories previously attached to tools or materials are suspended/ transcended for the bricoleur, these items can be put to whatever inventive purpose is necessary (42).

As bricoleur, Mary Poppins is a magnificent storyteller, who can see the imaginative and curative possibilities in a random event on the street – the appearance of a cow on Cherry Tree Lane occasions the story of “The Dancing Cow” to distract the attention of Jane from her splitting earache – or an uninteresting object on the mantelpiece: a kitsch porcelain cat, which is turned into the story of “The Cat that Looked at a King” to distract Michael’s attention from his post-birthday cake-eating toothache. Additionally, Mary Poppins has the magic and the creativity to organize an unforgettable New Year’s Eve party by piecing together and bringing alive the Banks siblings’ four favorite toys and three children’s books: *Robinson Crusoe*, *The Green Fairy Book* and *Mother Goose Nursery Rhymes* in the chapter entitled “Happy Ever After” in *Mary Poppins Opens the Door*.

3. Liminal Spaces and Periods of Transition in the *Mary Poppins* Books

As nanny and trickster, Mary Poppins is a liminal figure per se, that, naturally, exercises her magic in liminal places and during transitional periods of the day, of the month and of the year. While in the series, under the influence of Mary Poppins, all the places and spaces turn into transitional, liminal spaces, in the following paragraphs only the most characteristic and most frequented ones are going to be mentioned and discussed. These are: the nursery and the park, where the children spend most of their time; the space in-between, when they are swinging, floating, lifting and descending between the earth and the sky, and the liminal chronotopes: which are those parts of the day or those days of the year, which have a ritual significance, and which modify the rules and laws that operate in a specific space making the encounter of the inhabitants of various realms possible.

3.1. The Nursery and the Park

By custom, the Victorian and Edwardian nursery was a liminal place. In Arnold Van Gennep’s original understanding of the concept, liminal places were secluded spaces where the initiate or the initiates and their mentors could spend the ambiguous phase while they were outside of society but preparing to reenter it. As Georgia Grilli described it, the English nursery in the course of the 19th century and in the first decade of the 20th:

was an austere place filled with furniture and objects that could not be used anywhere else in the house. It was usually set off from the rest of the house, either located in the attics or in a separate wing of the house. It had its own stairs and outside entrance and the door leading to the rest of the house was often covered with a thick green curtain that muffled the noise of the children. The parents and servants hardly ever entered the nursery and knew very little about what went on inside as it was the place where the children were brought up, as if they didn’t belong to the reality and the world adults were actually involved and interested in. (...) The mother of the house may have appeared in the nursery at about 10:00 a.m., and the children would go down to the drawing room for afternoon tea—impeccably dressed and even more impeccably mannered. There was little more contact between the children and their parents than this. The presence of their governess totally filled the children’s lives.” (125, 127).

The nursery in the *Mary Poppins* books is, at the beginning of the series, as isolated as any of the Victorian and Edwardian English nurseries. Under the management of the

trickster nanny, it retains its liminal, secluded quality but it becomes a space with a more complex educational function: a base from which the children could be launched or lured into alternative universes; a safe space, where they feel secure and protected, and where they can return to rest, and to reflect upon the meaning(s) of their outstanding adventures, and a storage place for various magical objects, all the possessions of Mary Poppins.³

Besides the nursery, the space where the Banks children spend most of their time and from which some of their otherworldly exploits set off, or where even some outstanding adventures and meetings take place is the Park. P.L. Travers never tells the readers, which London park she had originally in her mind, but, taken into account the proximity of the zoo as well as the type of neighborhood that surrounds it, she may have had London's Regent's Park as a source of inspiration. Apart from these two details, the Park of the book can be any of London's royal parks with its lake, statues, well-tended gardens, and the occasional nooks and spaces filled wild flowers, and ignored or maybe overlooked by the rule-abiding Park Keeper. For the Banks children, the Park is the outside equivalent to their nursery. It gives them more opportunities for socializing, but strangely, they never meet real children of their own age there, so they continue their isolated existence playing among themselves under the supervision of Mary Poppins.

As a go in-between urban and rural, civilized and natural, public and private, the Park is, just as the aforementioned nursery, a liminal space by definition. Under the creative management of the trickster nanny it also becomes a meeting place of art and reality. At the beginning of the chapter entitled "The Park in the Park" in the volume *Mary Poppins in the Park*, Jane builds a miniature world out of branches, leaves, and plasticine figures that then come to life. The plasticine figures however refuse to believe that they are anything but "real," and Jane, Michael, and Mary Poppins descend into, and become involved in the adventures of this miniature world, which, though originally created by Jane, has already started to develop on its own. As it always happens, at the end of the day, the children return to the real world, but remain altered by their experience:

Crowned with the gold of the buttercup tree, Jane walked home under the maple boughs. All was quiet. The sun had set. The shadows of the Long Walk were falling all about her. And at the same time the brightness of the little Park folded her closely round. The dark of one, the light of the other—she felt them both together. "I am in two places at once," she whispered... (Travers: *Mary Poppins in the Park*, "Chapter Five: The Park in the Park")

3.2. Liminal Chronotopes and the Space in Between

Most of the Banks children's magic adventures, during which they enter alternate universes, take place on special days or periods of the month or the year: at Full Moon, on the eve of Christmas, on the eve of the New Year, at Halloween, on Midsummer's Eve etc.

³ the medicine bottle that contains everyone's favourite beverage, the thermometer and the tape measure, both of which measure good conduct, the parrot-headed umbrella that can talk and fly etc.

On these days the boundaries that separate animals from humans, the living from the dead, the sky from the earth, the sea from the earth are blurred: and the Zoo, the Park, the sea bed, the departments store etc. become liminal chronotopes: special meeting places (for a limited period of time) for creatures belonging to different realms and categories. These are the days in which the mythical meets the everyday, on which the particular becomes universal. On all of these occasions the children move in originally unfamiliar realms (the depth of the ocean, among constellations) rendered familiar, and manage to communicate with the creatures there. They usually embark on these adventures after bedtime, on their own accord, and on the invitation of a strange voice, which, as they soon find out, belongs to one of the inhabitants of the realm they are invited to discover. The owner of the voice acts as their guide. Mary Poppins never guides them herself, though she is always present. All of their exploits in parallel worlds and universes end in a ritual dance of some kind that is meant to unite and bring harmony among the various realms of the earth, the cosmos and the mythical world. At the end of the ritual dance, they fall asleep and are brought home by Mary Poppins. They never remember how they managed to return to the nursery. The next day they reflect on their experiences on their own, for their trickster nanny never acknowledges of having taken part in the adventure, let alone provide them with an explanation.

The “in-between space” between two opposing “realities”, as Georgia Grilli observed in her fascinating study: *Myth, Symbol and Meaning in Mary Poppins. The Governess as Provocateur* is an important and significant metaphor, a metaphor to which the *Mary Poppins* books frequently return (59). In the series there are, indeed, many occasions when characters are seen to be suspended, swinging between the sky and the earth, belonging to both dimensions and to neither

Up, up, she went, till her black straw hat was higher than the trees, then down she came with her neat black toes pointed towards the lawn. Her eyes, as she rode her flying swing, shone with a strange, bright gleam. They were bluer than Jane had ever seen them, blue with the blueness of far-away. They seemed to look past the trees and houses, and out beyond all the seas and mountains, and over the rim of the world. The five swings swung together. [...] [The children] were wrapped in a dream with Mary Poppins, a dream that swung them up and down between the earth and the sky, a rocking, riding, lulling dream ... (Travers: *Mary Poppins Opens the Door*, “Chapter Eight: The Other Door”)

Related to these experiences of physical “in-betweenness” is linked one of the few explicit teaching of Mary Poppins: “You can’t have anything for always” ... (Travers: “The Other Door” from *Mary Poppins Opens the Door*, “Chapter Eight: The Other Door”), for the only things one can be sure in life are not objects, individuals or events but periods of transition, change and loss.

Conclusion

The content of P.L. Travers’s *Mary Poppins* novels, as well as the intent that motivated their writing went/ goes well beyond the customary fare and scope of children’s literature.

What the authoress did in the series was more than a domestic tale spiced up with some tame adventures and magic tricks. She introduced the world to a new, modern trickster figure that united the independence and determination of the New Woman to the narcissism of the decadent Dandy, a trickster-nanny that displayed all the basic characteristics, and performed all the customary “chores” of the traditional mythical trickster, but who managed to stay respectable and asexual so as to fit in the nursery of the urban, late Victorian middle class bank clerk. P.L. Travers’s *Mary Poppins* series are a veritable mythography of the modern, western trickster, the chief function of whom is to instruct and to connect through laughter, dance, story and adventure children to their parents, humans and animals, animate and inanimate, real and mythical, the Earth and the Cosmos.

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